

A Scalable Swarm Intelligence Algorithm for Autonomous UAV Search and Rescue Operations

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and implementation of an autonomous UAV-based search and rescue system developed within the Horizon Europe project P2CODE. The proposed system leverages a modular and scalable architecture integrating edge-based real-time video processing, AI-based human detection, asynchronous message communication, and persistent state logging, all orchestrated through a web-based operator interface. Central to the system is a swarm intelligence algorithm that partitions the search area among multiple UAVs, taking into account factors such as battery levels and initial positions to generate balanced and coherent flight paths. By combining a Divide Areas based on Robots' initial Positions (DARP) method with a Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) algorithm, the system ensures efficient and complete coverage of large outdoor regions. The operational workflow supports both fully autonomous exploration and reactive human-in-the-loop intervention in response to real-time detections. This work contributes a practical blueprint for large-scale, multi-agent coordination in dynamic and unstructured environments, advancing the state of the art in autonomous search and rescue missions.

Index Terms—Swarm Intelligence, Object Detection, Search and Rescue, UAV coordination, Coverage path planning

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has become increasingly prominent in a wide range of applications, including infrastructure monitoring, environmental surveillance, and emergency response. Among these, search and rescue operations represent a particularly critical domain where UAVs can provide substantial benefits. Their ability to rapidly cover large, difficult-to-access areas without risking human lives makes them well-suited for locating missing persons in wilderness regions or in the aftermath of natural disasters. The coordination of multiple UAVs, often referred to as a drone swarm, can further enhance the effectiveness of these missions by enabling parallelized exploration and adaptive behaviors in response to dynamic conditions.

This work was funded by the EU Horizon P2CODE (“Programming Platform for Intelligent Collaborative Deployments over Heterogeneous Edge-IoT Environments”) project under the Grant number HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-03/101093069.

This paper presents the outcomes of a specific use case developed within the scope of the European project P2CODE (Programming Platform for Intelligent Collaborative Deployments) [1]. P2CODE is a Horizon Europe research initiative that aims to develop an open, secure, and trustworthy platform for the dynamic deployment and orchestration of distributed applications across the device–edge–core–cloud continuum. The platform supports the programmability and coordination of large-scale intelligent systems, offering developers a unified framework for secure and resilient multi-device orchestration. Among its application domains is Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR), where P2CODE provides the technological foundation for coordinating robotic assets in time-critical scenarios. The work described herein focuses on a search-and-rescue scenario in which a swarm of UAVs is deployed to autonomously explore a large outdoor area in search of missing individuals. The aim is to exploit the advantages of distributed aerial coordination to enhance search efficiency, reduce overall mission duration, and enable real-time responsiveness when potential victims are detected. The system integrates edge-based video processing, AI-based human detection, persistent mission logging, and a swarm intelligence planning algorithm, all orchestrated through P2CODE’s runtime infrastructure to ensure scalability, traceability, and operational robustness.

The primary focus of this paper is the design and integration of a swarm intelligence algorithm within the mission planner, emphasizing its suitability for scalable multi-UAV search and rescue operations. We detail how the algorithm partitions the search area and coordinates multiple UAVs by accounting for factors such as initial positions, battery levels, and mission constraints, ultimately generating balanced and coherent paths for each agent. These design considerations are critical for ensuring responsive, efficient, and fully autonomous exploration in real-world scenarios. By describing the algorithm’s adaptation to the aerial domain and its integration into a modular system architecture, this work provides a practical foundation for future experimental validation and contributes to the broader field of autonomous multi-agent coordination

in dynamic environments.

In summary the main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- The design of a modular and scalable architecture for multi-UAV autonomous search and rescue missions, integrating real-time AI-based human detection, persistent logging, and operator supervision tools.
- The adaptation of a swarm intelligence-based planning algorithm (combining DARP and STC) to the aerial domain, accounting for UAV-specific constraints such as flight dynamics and battery status.
- A comprehensive description of the operational workflow, covering mission initialization, autonomous exploration, real-time detection, and operator-in-the-loop intervention, forming a blueprint for future real-world deployment and experimentation.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II provides a review of the related literature on UAV swarm coordination and path planning algorithms, with particular attention to approaches based on swarm intelligence. Section III describes the architecture of the developed system, detailing the integration of its key components and communication infrastructure. Section IV presents the swarm intelligence algorithm implemented in the mission planner, including its design rationale. Section V explains the operational workflow of the system. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The application of swarm intelligence to UAV-based search and rescue (SAR) has emerged as a promising strategy to address the inherent challenges of coverage, coordination, and efficiency in large and unstructured environments [2], [3]. Swarm intelligence draws inspiration from biological systems, particularly the collective behaviors of insects and animals, to enable decentralized and adaptive coordination among agents. In the context of UAVs, such algorithms facilitate scalable collaboration without relying on centralized control, which is crucial for time-sensitive SAR missions.

Recent studies have explored diverse swarm coordination strategies for UAVs, including ant colony optimization [4], [5], particle swarm optimization [6], and biologically inspired flocking behaviors [7]. Among these, coverage path planning (CPP) methods have gained particular attention for SAR tasks. The multi-robot coverage path planning (mCPP) problem [8] highlights the computational complexity of assigning agents to subregions in a way that ensures full coverage with minimal redundancy. A widely adopted approach for mCPP is the Divide Areas Algorithm for Optimal Multi-Robot Coverage Path Planning (DARP) algorithm proposed by Kapoutsis et al. [9], which partitions the search area based on initial positions and aims for spatially coherent and load-balanced assignments.

In aerial domains, the adaptation of ground-based methods like DARP involves additional constraints, including flight dynamics, energy constraints, and no-fly zones. Gabriely and Rimon introduced the Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) method

[10], often used as a local path planner once regions are assigned. This method ensures that each UAV follows an efficient path through its assigned subregion.

The integration of swarm coordination with real-time human detection further enhances SAR effectiveness. Recent advances in deep learning-based object detection—such as YOLOv4 by Bochkovskiy et al. [11]—offer accurate and efficient performance on UAV platforms. Other papers also demonstrated real-time detection of humans using YOLOv4 adaptations for aerial perspectives [12], [13], showing promise for onboard inference and fast decision-making in the field.

Altogether, the convergence of decentralized planning algorithms, UAV-specific adaptations, and efficient onboard vision enables robust and scalable systems for autonomous SAR missions, particularly in scenarios requiring fast, wide-area coverage and real-time responsiveness.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system developed for Application Area 4 of the P2CODE [1] project addresses the autonomous coordination of a swarm of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) for the purpose of search and rescue in large-scale outdoor environments. The architecture is designed to ensure modularity, scalability, and robustness by integrating real-time video analytics, asynchronous message-based communication, persistent state logging, and operator supervision through a graphical interface. An overview of the complete system architecture is presented in Figure 1.

A. Aerial Platform

The aerial platform employed consists of *DJI Mini 3* UAVs. These are lightweight quadcopters (weighing under 250 grams) capable of capturing 4K HDR video and equipped with a 1/1.3" CMOS sensor optimized for high-resolution imagery under varying lighting conditions. Each drone is operated via a custom-developed mobile application built upon the DJI Software Development Kit (SDK) [14]. This application enables the automatic execution of missions, real-time telemetry extraction (including GPS coordinates, orientation, and battery status), and continuous video streaming using RTMP or RTSP protocols.

B. Video Ingestion and Distribution

All video streams transmitted by the UAVs are initially received by the *VideoProxy* component based on MediaMTX [15], which is responsible for distributing the video to both the AI modules and the operator interface. Specifically, the proxy forwards each stream to one or more AI-based detection modules for processing and simultaneously republishes the video to the *Commander Frontend*, allowing human operators to view live UAV footage. This bifurcation of the stream ensures minimal latency in both detection and human-in-the-loop decision making.

Fig. 1. System architecture for Application Area 4: UAV-based autonomous exploration and detection.

C. Human Detection Module

Each video stream is processed by a dedicated instance of the *Human Detector AI* module. This component implements a deep learning-based object detection model derived from YOLOv4 [11], optimized for detecting small-scale objects in aerial imagery. The architectural details of the model are described in [16], where the authors propose improvements including multi-scale feature aggregation and customized anchor box configurations tailored to aerial views of human targets. The model achieves real-time performance and is deployed on a GPU-enabled edge server to support concurrent inference on multiple streams. Detections produced by this module include bounding box coordinates, classification confidence, and associated metadata, and are published to the message bus for downstream consumption.

D. Communication and Data Persistence

A central element of the system is the *MessageBus*, implemented using the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) via RabbitMQ [17]. It enables decoupled, asynchronous communication between all system components through topic-based publish-subscribe mechanisms. The primary topics include:

- **telemetry**: real-time UAV state including GPS position, battery level, and sensor status.
- **detections**: structured outputs from the AI detectors, including timestamps and image coordinates.
- **mission_updates**: planning results and control commands issued by the mission planner.

To ensure traceability and support fault diagnosis, the system incorporates an *AMQP Persistor*. This component

subscribes to all topics in the message bus and stores the complete stream of messages in a MongoDB-based database. By capturing the full operational state of the system, it facilitates detailed post-mission analysis and provides the necessary information for rapid debugging and resolution of system faults.

E. AI Mission Planning

Mission planning is performed by the *AI Mission Planner*, which implements a swarm intelligence algorithm adapted from the Divide Areas based on Robots' initial Positions (DARP) method [9]. The planner takes as input the region of interest and the current state of all UAVs (including position and battery status), and produces a coordinated set of waypoints to ensure complete area coverage. In the event of a detection, the operator may request a delivery mission, in which case the planner computes a new trajectory for a designated UAV to carry and deliver assistance (e.g., first-aid supplies) to the detected location. The output of the planner is published to the message bus and logged persistently for monitoring and analysis.

F. Command and Control Interface

The *Commander Backend* serves as the interface between the internal components of the system and the *Commander Frontend*, a web-based graphical user interface. The backend aggregates information from both the message bus and the database and relays it to the frontend in real time. The Commander Frontend presents the operator with a complete view of the mission, including:

- live video streams from active UAVs,

- telemetry and health status of each drone,
- map-based visualization of detections and flight paths,
- controls to initiate exploration or delivery missions.

This interface enables the operator to maintain situational awareness and to make informed decisions during the mission, either by initiating new plans or by responding to autonomous detection events.

G. Scalability and Operational Characteristics

The architecture has been designed to support scalability across multiple dimensions. Video processing components, including the human detector modules and video proxy, can be replicated to accommodate additional UAVs. The message bus supports concurrent data streams and high-throughput communication. The planner and database components ensure that mission coordination and historical logging remain consistent even as the system scales.

Connectivity requirements are annotated in Figure 1, indicating which modules require GPU acceleration (e.g., Human Detector), persistence guarantees (e.g., MongoDB and AMQP Persistor), or external access (e.g., Commander Frontend).

IV. SWARM INTELLIGENCE-BASED MISSION PLANNING

In this work, the task of coordinating a team of UAVs to perform complete area coverage is addressed using a swarm intelligence algorithm adapted from the Divide Areas based on Robots' initial Positions (DARP) method [9]. Originally developed for ground robots, DARP has been modified in our system to operate effectively in aerial search and rescue missions, where a fleet of UAVs must cover large, potentially unstructured areas efficiently and reliably.

The coverage path planning problem is formally defined as the task of generating collision-free paths that collectively ensure complete coverage of a known region, while minimizing the overall mission time. In the multi-robot case (mCPP) [18], the problem becomes particularly challenging due to its combinatorial complexity. The DARP algorithm addresses this by decomposing the area of interest into disjoint subregions, each assigned to a single agent, and by optimizing the allocation such that the resulting paths are spatially coherent, load-balanced, and aligned with the initial positions of the UAVs.

A. Area Partitioning via DARP

The algorithm begins by discretizing the region of interest into a regular grid. Given the number of UAVs and their initial positions, the DARP algorithm constructs a set of evaluation matrices, one for each UAV, which encode the distance between each cell in the region and the UAV's current position. Based on these matrices, an initial assignment of cells is performed, typically resulting in a Voronoi-like partitioning [19].

To achieve balanced workloads, a cost function is defined that penalizes unequal area assignments. The algorithm iteratively adjusts scalar weighting factors applied to the evaluation matrices in order to minimize the deviation from a uniform

partition. This optimization is carried out using a cyclic coordinate descent approach, which ensures that each UAV receives a subregion with approximately the same number of cells.

Connectivity of assigned subregions is enforced by incorporating a spatial continuity constraint. When a UAV is assigned disconnected cells, the evaluation matrix is modified to penalize distant or isolated regions, encouraging the assignment of contiguous, compact areas. This guarantees that each UAV can cover its designated subregion without redundant traversal or inter-area transitions.

B. Path Planning via Spanning Tree Coverage

Once the terrain is partitioned into UAV-specific subregions, the algorithm delegates the computation of individual paths to a single-agent planner. In our case, we adopt a variant of the Spanning Tree Coverage (STC) algorithm [10]. Each UAV constructs a minimum spanning tree (MST) [20] over its assigned cells and then generates a traversal path by circumnavigating the MST in a fixed direction. This strategy ensures full coverage while minimizing overlap and backtracking.

C. Adaptation to Aerial Domain

The transition from ground robots to aerial vehicles requires specific adaptations. First, the terrain representation must consider altitude constraints and potential no-fly zones, which are treated analogously to obstacles. Second, UAVs can traverse regions in three dimensions, which allows greater flexibility in movement planning, but also requires accounting for flight dynamics, energy constraints, and line-of-sight communication.

To accommodate these requirements, we extend the evaluation matrices to incorporate flight-related costs, such as energy consumption or expected wind resistance. Additionally, the mission planner interfaces with real-time telemetry data and environmental maps to dynamically refine the assigned paths if mission conditions change, such as the detection of a human presence or the failure of a UAV.

D. Algorithmic Complexity and Scalability

The computational complexity of the DARP algorithm, in its approximate form, grows polynomially with respect to both the number of UAVs and the size of the discretized search area. Specifically, for a grid of n cells and r UAVs, the area division phase has a time complexity bounded by $\mathcal{O}(r \cdot n \cdot \text{MaxIter})$, where MaxIter depends nonlinearly on the initial configuration and problem geometry. In practice, however, convergence is reached in a reasonable number of iterations for operationally relevant input sizes. The path generation phase for each UAV is computed independently, enabling full parallelization.

This property is essential for real-time mission planning in search and rescue scenarios, where responsiveness and adaptability are critical. In our evaluation, we analyze how the algorithm's performance scales with the number of UAVs and the size of the region, assessing both computational cost and coverage efficiency.

Fig. 2. Command UI with drones information.

V. OPERATIONAL WORKFLOW

This section outlines the end-to-end operational workflow of the UAV swarm system designed for autonomous search and rescue missions. The process involves continuous monitoring, mission planning, autonomous flight execution, real-time video processing, and responsive mission adaptation in the event of detections.

A. Mission Monitoring and Initialization

The mission begins with the human operator, referred to as the *Commander*, accessing the *Commander Frontend*, a graphical user interface that provides a comprehensive overview of the system state. Through this interface, the Commander monitors key metrics for each UAV, including availability, battery level, geographic location, and mission status (see Fig. 2). The interface also displays live video streams from all active UAVs and visual overlays of system events, such as detected objects or assigned waypoints.

B. Exploration Request and Mission Planning

Once the area suspected to contain missing persons is identified, the Commander uses the UI to define a polygonal *Region of Interest (ROI)*. Upon confirmation, the system initiates a request to the *AI Mission Planner* to compute an exploration plan (see Fig. 3).

The mission planner executes a swarm intelligence algorithm, as described in Section IV, which partitions the ROI into a set of disjoint subregions, one for each available UAV. This partitioning is computed based on a variety of parameters, including the number of UAVs, their current battery levels, and their initial positions. The objective is to minimize total exploration time and ensure balanced coverage. Each resulting subregion is converted into a series of GPS waypoints that define the path the corresponding UAV must follow to cover its assigned area (see Fig. 4).

C. Autonomous Flight Execution and Video Processing

Upon receiving its assigned waypoints, each UAV initiates autonomous flight and begins executing its mission. The UAVs operate without human intervention, navigating their assigned paths and continuously streaming video to the edge node. These video streams are received by the *VideoProxy*, which

Fig. 3. Commander defining the region of interest.

Fig. 4. Commander UI with the paths defined for each drone by the swarm intelligence algorithm.

forwards them to both the *Commander Frontend* and the *Human Detector AI* module (see Fig. 5).

The AI module processes each video stream in real time using a custom object detection model optimized for aerial imagery. The model detects potential human targets and generates detection messages, including bounding boxes and confidence scores. These messages are published to the message bus and stored in the database for traceability.

D. Detection Handling and Reactive Intervention

If a UAV detects a potential missing person, the detection is immediately visualized both on the UAV's onboard interface and on the Commander Frontend. The system highlights the detection on a georeferenced map and displays the corresponding video frame, enabling the Commander to quickly assess the situation.

In response, the Commander may choose to trigger a follow-up mission. This typically involves dispatching a secondary UAV to the detection site to deliver essential supplies, such as first-aid materials or communication devices. The follow-up mission is processed through the same mission planner, which selects an appropriate UAV (considering availability and proximity) and generates a direct trajectory to the target location.

E. Mission Continuation and Finalization

Following a detection or upon completion of their assigned exploration tasks, UAVs either return to a predefined base

Fig. 5. Drones following the defined path for them while executing the AI people detection algorithm.

station or await further instructions depending on mission configuration. All operational data—including telemetry, detection logs, and mission execution traces—are recorded by the *AMQP Persistor* in the MongoDB database, ensuring full traceability and enabling post-mission analysis.

This operational workflow enables rapid deployment, autonomous search, and human-in-the-loop decision-making, while maintaining system transparency and robustness through persistent monitoring and data logging.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a comprehensive system for autonomous search and rescue missions using a coordinated swarm of UAVs, developed within the framework of the European Horizon Europe project P2CODE. The proposed architecture integrates a modular set of edge-deployed components, including real-time video ingestion, AI-based human detection, asynchronous message communication, persistent state logging, and a web-based operator interface. Central to the system is a swarm intelligence algorithm that enables the optimal division of a mission area among multiple UAVs based on criteria such as initial position and battery status, facilitating balanced, efficient, and fully autonomous aerial exploration.

The operational workflow of the system supports both proactive and reactive mission strategies: operators can proactively initiate and configure missions while retaining the ability to react to detection events in real time, providing a human-in-the-loop capability that enhances safety and flexibility. The architecture's parallelizable components and asynchronous communication model are intended to ensure scalability, making it feasible to deploy larger UAV teams and tackle more challenging mission profiles without significant performance degradation.

Future work will focus on several key areas to enhance the system's effectiveness and operational maturity. Planned developments include large-scale field testing under diverse real-world conditions to validate performance and reliability; the integration of dynamic re-planning mechanisms to enable UAVs to adapt their paths and roles in response to evolving mission scenarios or environmental changes; and the extension of the framework to support heterogeneous multi-robot teams,

combining UAVs with ground or marine robots for more comprehensive SAR coverage. Additional research will aim to improve the robustness of the detection pipeline against adverse weather and low-light conditions, and to incorporate learning-based strategies that allow the swarm to continuously refine its behaviour based on accumulated mission data and operator feedback. Together, these enhancements will bring the system closer to practical deployment in critical SAR operations, supporting faster, safer, and more effective responses to emergencies.

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